

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DAINKEH****FIRST NAME: ATUMANNI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author use MSWord 2013 on Windows 10

Concepts:

1. The process of good essay writing (EUCLID 2021,7-12)
2. Standard British English versus Standard American English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Use of Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Scholarly or academic writing is unique in that it seeks to answer a hypothesis as well as communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2021, 7). Having read the seventy-two pages of the EUCLID 2021 ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one (1), I have been able to learn aspects of my writing that I had taken for granted by believing that I was doing the right thing.

The two videos on the course pack ACA-401/ACA-401D provided me with an excellent refresher and summary on the use of Microsoft Word. The sample review video by Dr. Gulma not only enlightened me on the use of track changes but also provided an understanding of some of the common errors in writing an academic paper. For example, the need to avoid contractions, proper referencing, and citations, to name a few. Similarly, Prof. Cleenewerck's video on the rule of style using a response paper template provided me with concrete and pragmatic learning. The difference between a Rule of style and a Paragraph style, as well as how to access the Oxford Rule of Style, were a great takeaway for me.

Writing an essay into three main domains: introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10) gives it a structure as well as a logical and coherent flow.

My initial reaction to being accepted by Euclid University for doctoral studies was one of elation. This, however, quickly dissipated when I started thinking of the workload that lay ahead. This was because of the time lapse since my second master's degree studies.

Following my successful log-in into the Learning Management System (LMS), I started feeling a sense of reassurance after reading through the systematic planning of the doctoral program and the level of support by the University at my disposal. The course pack provided the basics that I needed for a return to academic work at this level.

This paper discusses five concepts (as recommended in the response paper guidance) in the following order:

1. The process of good essay writing
2. Standard British English versus Standard American English
3. Plagiarism
4. Style guide
5. Use of Latin abbreviations

2) THE PROCESS OF GOOD ESSAY WRITING

I called this a process because of its multiple stages. The first of these stages is often the psychological engagement with the subject matter, characterized by distress, rumination, and procrastination before having enough courage to start.

Having a plan is critical in guiding the process and the pyramid of steps, starting from analyzing the question to handing in the essay outlined in the course pack (EUCLID 2021, 8) succinctly outlined. An essay plan is not done in a vacuum; therefore, reading around the topic and identifying pertinent aspects of the topic help in refining ideas before drawing up an essay plan (EUCLID 2021, 9).

When it comes to the style of writing an essay, a good introduction gives the reader an insatiable quest to continue reading the essay with a clear understanding of what the reader should expect.

Time management is critical in the process of essay writing; it is advisable to write a paragraph on an aspect that has been fully grasped for a short period than to seek to write the entire essay in one sitting. This approach provides a sense of progress as well as reduces the anxiety associated with meeting the deadline for handing in an essay.

Good time management enables the writer to make provisions for editing. Editing before handing in an essay is critical because it gives the writer the best opportunity to make improvements to the essay with a fresh pair of eyes, mainly because he or she will

have developed more confidence and less anxiety about the writing process (EUCLID 2021, 11).

Stating the central thesis of the essay from the outset, staying focused on the subject matter under discussion, clarity of writing with short, unambiguous sentences, and avoiding generalities and plagiarism are critical requirements of a scholarly essay (EUCLID 2021, 13).

3) STANDARD BRITISH ENGLISH VERSUS STANDARD AMERICAN ENGLISH

Academic or scholarly essay writing is guided by rules, and one of such rules is the choice of a variant of the English language (EUCLID 2021, 25). It is essential to choose the English language variant from the outset when writing an academic essay. The need for rules in writing an essay is to maintain consistency. The two common variants of English are Standard British English (SBE) and Standard American English (SAE). Both variants share more similarities than differences (EUCLID 2021, 25).

It is worth writing since World War II, SAE has grown in tandem with the country's growth in various spheres, including political, economic, technical, and global influence. SBE differs from SAE concerning the pronunciation of some words even when they have the same spelling; differences in spelling for others that have the same pronunciation whilst others that are pronounced the same carry additional meaning. There are also differences in writing dates and use of punctuation marks such as commas, periods, and quotations (EUCLID 2021, 26).

On reflection, I realized that I have been oscillating between SBE and SAE in my previous works but always mindful of the need to avoid plagiarism.

4) PLAGIARISM

EUCLID 2021, 34 defines plagiarism as a situation “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information”. Plagiarism is an academic offense that can be committed unwillingly. It is wrong for several reasons, namely:

- a. It is unfair to the originator of the piece of academic material not to give him or her credit by acknowledging the piece of work.
- b. It is unethical
- c. It is an academic offense with potentially serious consequences. Mercifully, plagiarism is avoidable. This can be done by appropriately citing the author. EUCLID (2021, 35) recommends two types of citations to avoid plagiarism.

These are in-text and a list of works citations. In-text citation (which I have often used) takes the form of either quotation or paraphrasing.

I realized after reading the course pack ACA-401/ACA-401D (Period 1) with a keen interest in chapter four that my frequent use of quotations in previous works was inappropriately done.

I have learned from this chapter that the fewer quotations in an essay, the better its originality. The circumstances under which quotations can be used have been made clear in this chapter of the course pack.

Appropriate paragraphing is also covered in the chapter with specific and clear examples. Although citation is a good way to avoid the offense of plagiarism, I note that citing unnecessarily is inappropriate. A citation is unnecessary when the information cited is generally known by the public.

5) STYLE GUIDE

EUCLID (2021, 41) defines a style guide as “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent”. Style entails a range of aspects in writing that include, but are not limited to, the use of punctuations, choice of English language variant, length of sentences, font size, and the list goes on. A key advantage of using a Rule of style in academic writing is the maintenance of consistency, consequently saving time in proofreading and correction. Although style guides are generally associated with technical, commercial, and other writing enterprises that require more than one author, a rule of style is highly recommended at EUCLID University for the reasons cited above. The recommended Rule of style is the Chicago (Turabian) Rule of style, EUCLID (2021, 41).

The video by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck, ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack (period 1), further explained how to use styles, the difference between a rule of style and Paragraph style as well as ways of accessing the Oxford Rule of Style.

Arguably, I hold the view that the use of a style guide in writing carries the risk of limiting a writer from using his or her full potential in writing. Maintaining a style guide in my view restricts the full demonstration of a writer’s skills.

One of the most interesting points that I learned from this course pack is the use of the first person singular in academic writing. I have always held the view, following corrections from previous works, that it is wrong to do so.

Euclid University template enormously helps in addressing most of the issues relating to style. Given the flexibility in the choice of English variant allowed by the university, I have opted for the SBE because it is the variant that I have used over the years.

6) USE OF LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

I previously used several of the Latin abbreviations provided in the course pack but only fully know their meanings now!

I selected this as one of my five concepts, because of my experience of reading papers where I often had to look at a dictionary for the meaning of words in a sentence that could be made simpler.

I have read abbreviations for instance such as cf, pp, ex, officio, and vise, without fully understanding their meanings except to deduce from the context in which they are used in a sentence or looking them up in a dictionary. I agree that because Latin abbreviations have the potential to cause misunderstanding, their use should be limited, if not entirely avoided.

7) CONCLUSION

The study pack has been enormously helpful. It is well laid out, with chapter eight, the last chapter, serving as an excellent example of how a response paper is reviewed using track changes. I got a good grounding from the first chapter of the course pack, whilst the sections on plagiarism, the use of a Rule of style, and the differences between Standard British English and Standard American English created a moment of reflection on my oscillatory use of both variants in my previous works. Similarly, the use of in-text and a list of works referencing provided a clear difference between scholarly and ordinary writing.

Period one has been insightful with the material in the course pack, greatly helping to allay my anxiety about starting a doctoral program.

REFERENCES

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